

A new romance between taxonomic literature and specimen data? News from Paris

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Natural history researchers manipulate a great deal of resources, among which publications and archives play a critical part. However, biodiversity literature databases have historically developed independently from specimen and Museum databases, each community following different standards.

The digital Age did not really improve things: most current databases describing specimens and documents (notably at MNHN) are using heterogeneous formats and ontologies. It prevents researchers from the full exploitation of data potential for lack of aggregation or linkage of resources still in silos.

The proposed communication will present the overall vision and some specific projects designed by MNHN to challenge this situation, with a global intention to address the Holy Grail of the "extended specimen".

We will start with a progress report on the Datapoc project (whose initial goals were presented at the Biodiversity Next conference in 2019). It aims at demonstrating the potential of data aggregation and search through various local and national databases (natural collection databases, library catalogues, academic press, open archives), using the "person" and related unique identifiers as a linking key.

We will then consider the potential of unique identifiers for articles in serials. In taxonomic practise, whenever a specimen is published, the author is expected to cite the article having originally described it. This is not an easy task for retrospectively digitized publications as those available in biodiversity digital libraries, as they generally cannot be cited at the article level, only at the issue level. MNHN library is currently using BHL to "segment" digitized issues in articles; in a next step, DOIs will be assigned to these articles.

These two examples will illustrate some of the principles upon which a more ambitious project is currently being launched in Paris: the full redesign of MNHN collection and research Information System. Its goal is not to merge all data in a common store but to create smarter bridges between existing silos and communities. To that end, the use of common standards and identifiers will be a critical factor of success. More importantly even, it will challenge our capacity to align professional habits and curation practises among MNHN collections staff.

